

ANALYTICAL USES OF NESSLER'S REAGENT. PART III.
ESTIMATION OF FORMALDEHYDE, PYROGALLOL,
TANNIC AND GALLIC ACIDS, THEIR ABSOLUTE
OXYGEN VALUES.

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In previous papers on the subject (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 714 ; 1936, 13, 73, 315) it has been shown by one of us that alkaline solution of potassium mercuric iodide in presence of reducing sugars gives up iodine, by which they are oxidised, and liberates corresponding amount of mercury according to the degree of reducibilities of the latter, the complex breaking up thus:—

This reaction has been previously utilised in estimating formaldehyde in concentrated solution (Gross and Bougoult, *J. Pharm. chim.*, 1922, 26, 5, 170). It was thought interesting to see whether this method could be utilised in the micro-estimation of CH_2O , and whether the reaction

is absolute and strictly quantitative. For this purpose definite amount of pure dry hexamethylenetetramine was distilled with dilute sulphuric acid (reagent) at 100° and the distillate was absorbed in alkaline Nessler's solution. The mercury liberated was dissolved in standard iodine solution and the excess of the latter was titrated back. The results obtained were found to conform strictly to the above equation. The micro-estimation also gave excellent results and a dilution of 1 in 100,000 was estimated with fair degree of accuracy. This encouraged us to see the applicability of the method in finding out the absolute oxygen value of pyrogallol and, therefore, in estimating it quantitatively. Previous experimenters have given different results about the capacity of alkaline pyrogallol to absorb oxygen (Berthelot, *Compt. rend.*, 1893, 1066, 1459; Zorkocyz, *Biochem. Z.*, 1925, 161). Thus Berthelot (*loc. cit.*) found that according to the nature and strength of the alkali used, the absorption varied from 1.3 atoms of oxygen per molecule of pyrogallol, whereas according to Zorkocyz it goes beyond to 5 atoms. By the application of potassium mercuric iodide method constant

results were obtained and it was found that one molecule of pyrogallol always liberated two atoms of mercury corresponding to two atoms of oxygen. The experiments were done in absence of oxygen. This led us to examine the reducibilities of tannic and gallic acids. Unlike pyrogallol these estimations could be done in open air and it was found that one molecule of tannin (pentadigalloylglucose) absorbed 16 atoms of oxygen, whilst 4 molecules of gallic acid took 11 atoms. Various dilutions have been tested and fairly accurate results have been obtained. The method can, therefore, be suitably applied for their quantitative estimations.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Absolute Oxygen Value and Micro-estimation of Formaldehyde.

Hexamethylenetetramine solution (5 c.c.; 250 c.c. containing 0.030201 g.) corresponding to 0.007767 g. of CH_2O , was taken in a flask fitted with a dropping funnel, trap and a condenser; the end of the latter was connected with a funnel and fitted in a wide-mouthed bottle containing alkaline Nessler's solution. This was followed by a second bottle containing the same solution and serving as a guard. The Nessler's solution used in this and other experiments described in the paper was of the following strength:— 2.5 g. of HgCl_2 ; 8 g. of KI ; 100 c.c. of water; 50 c.c. of 30 % NaOH . Pure H_2SO_4 (15 %, 35 c.c.) was added from the funnel to the tetramine solution and the whole was distilled; mercury was precipitated in the first bottle, the second one remaining practically unaffected. The solutions of both were mixed, acidified with glacial acetic acid and standard iodine solution added. After the liberated mercury dissolved, the excess of iodine was titrated back. Several similar distillations were done and the following are some of the results.

TABLE I.

CH_2O actual in 5 c.c. calculated from $(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$.	CH_2O found calc. on the basis that each mol. takes 1 atom of oxygen.
0.007767 g.	0.007668 g.
"	0.007752
"	0.0078349
"	0.007752

Micro-estimation.—Pure formaldehyde solution of definite strength was prepared from $(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{N}_4$ by distillation with pure sulphuric acid. Micro-estimation was done using $N/100$ -thiosulphate and iodine solutions. The following are some of the results.

TABLE II.

Actual CH_2O present.	CH_2O found.
0.0525 %	0.0525 %
0.0217	0.0211
0.0108	0.01056
0.00534	0.00559
0.00107	0.00091

Absolute Oxygen Value of Pyrogallol and its Estimation.

The experiment was done in the apparatus shown in Fig. 1. It was

FIG. 1.

made air-free by means of coal gas purified and freed from oxygen by passing it successively through alkaline pyrogallol, bromine water, caustic soda and sulphuric acid. Carefully prepared air-free water was used to prepare standard pyrogallol (S_1) and Nessler's solution (S_3). The pushing up of these

solutions and glacial acetic acid (S_2) in the burette B (for S_1) and in the graduated funnel F (for S_2 and S_3) as well as the introduction of them in R, the reaction vessel, were all done in the atmosphere of coal gas by opening and closing the respective stop-cocks t_1-t_{11} , T_1 and the two-way cock T_2 (connecting B with R and B with S_1) and by using one or more of the the water seals w_1-w_4 to drive off air or to release the gas pressure inside the system. At first the whole apparatus was made air-free with empty S_1 , then closing all other stop-cocks, the latter was detached and standard pyrogallol was quickly introduced in it which was then connected with the system and made air-free by closing and opening the relevant stop-cocks. This precaution was necessary as it was undesirable to pass all the air of the system through pyrogallol solution:

The apparatus was made air-free in the following way:—

Parts made air-free.	Stop-cocks closed.	Stop-cocks opened.
Tube containing t_8-t_{11}	t_3	t_8-t_{11}
S_1	t_8-t_{10} , T_2, t_2	T_1 (connecting B with S_1), t_3, t_4, t_{11} .
S_2	T_2, t_2, t_4, t_7, t_8	t_3, t_6, t_9-t_{11} .
S_3	T_2, t_2, t_4, t_6, t_9	t_3, t_7, t_{10}, t_{11} .
F	T_2, t_4, t_6-t_8	t_9, t_3 .
F&R	T_1, t_3, t_4, t_6-t_8	T_2, t_1, t_3 .
F,R&B	$t_{11}, t_9, t_4, t_6-t_8$	T_1 (connecting B with R), T_2, t_3, t_6 .
Tube containing t_4 & t_5	T_1, T_2, t_3, t_6-t_8	t_3-t_5 .

The solutions were pushed up in the following way:—

Solution contained in	Stop-cocks closed.	Stop-cocks opened.
S_1	t_3, t_6, t_7, t_{11}	T_1 (con. B with S_1), t_6, t_8-t_{10} .

(The pressure was released by opening t_{11} and closing T_1 ; the liquid B is adjusted to the desired mark by connecting B and S_1 by T_1)

Solutions contained in	Stop-cocks closed.	Stop-cocks opened.
S_2	t_3, t_5, t_{10}, T_2	$t_7 - t_8, t_9$

(The pressure was released by opening t_{10} and t_{11})

S_3	t_3, t_8, T_3	t_8, t_9, t_9
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(The pressure was released by opening $t_3 - t_{11}$)

The solutions were introduced in R in the following way:—

Solution.	Stop-cocks closed.	Stop-cocks opened.
Standard pyrogallol from B	$t_3, t_5 - t_{11}, T_3$	t_3, t_4, t_1, T_1 (connecting B with R).
Nessler's solution and glacial acetic acid from F.	$t_4 - t_{11}, t_3$	t_3, T_2, t_1 .

Measured amount of the standard solution was taken in R from the burette and Nessler's solution and glacial acetic acid (10 c.c. each) were added in succession from the graduated funnel. Without disturbing the apparatus R was detached and the mercury liberated was dissolved in standard iodine solution (10 c.c.), the excess of the latter was then at once titrated back. The following are the results:—

TABLE III.

Thiosulphate = 0.1042N.

Pyrogallol in 250 c.c.	Vol. taken.	Thiosulphate required		Pyrogallol	
		Before oxidation (A).	After oxidation (B).	Found : (A - B) × thio × 0.00315.	Actual.
0.1907 g.	10 c.c.	8.8 c.c.	6.5 c.c.	0.007549 g.	0.007628 g.
0.4960	1	„	8.2	0.001969	0.001984
1.2551	1	„	7.25	0.005087	0.00502
2.3412	1	„	5.9	0.009517	0.009361

Pyrogallol found was calculated on the basis that one molecule takes two atoms of oxygen.

Oxygen Value and Estimation of Tannic and Gallic Acids.

Unlike pyrogallol tannic and gallic acids could be treated in open air. The procedure was the same.

Merck's tannic acid (guaranteed reagent, Pentadigalloylglucose, M. W. 1700) was taken. The following are the results :

TABLE IV.

0.05112 N-Thiosulphate and 10 c.c. of iodine were used.

Tannic acid in 250 c.c.	Vol. added.	Thiosulphate required Before oxida- tion (A).	Thiosulphate required After oxida- tion (B).	Tannic acid Found : (A - B) × thio. × 0.0053.	Actual.
0.3020 g.	10 c.c.	15.5 c.c.	11 c.c.	0.01219 g.	0.01208 g.
0.7373	1	„	14.35	0.003116	0.002940
1.1919	1	„	13.7	0.004877	0.004768
2.2988	1	„	12.1	0.009212	0.009195

Tannic acid found was calculated on the basis that 16 atoms of oxygen were required for one molecule.

Merck's pure gallic acid was taken and recrystallised from hot water. The following are the results: (Gallic acid found was calculated on the basis that 4 molecules required 11 atoms of oxygen).

TABLE V.

Gallic acid in 250 c.c.	Vol. added.	Thiosulphate required. Before oxida- tion (A).	Thiosulphate required. After oxida- tion (B).	Gallic acid Found : (A - B) × thio × 0.0053.	Actual.
0.2775 g.	10 c.c.	17.2 c.c.	10.55 c.c.	0.01135	0.01110
0.3614		„	8.55	0.01452	0.01446
1.2019	1	„	14.3	0.004938	0.004808